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MEN'S LIVES MATTERS – SUICIDES BY MEN

STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH

TRUTH IS OUT HERE

Date: 31/March/2021

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Summary: Study on Men's Health and Suicide by Men covers a broad range of research on men's health and wellbeing. What causes men to die young or cut short their lives? How do false cases which the Supreme Court of India has called "legal terrorism", daily abuse and harassment by women against her male partner by using "women-centric" laws in India affect men's mental health. This report is not a comprehensive review of the available literature but provides a broad overview of the topic. It is an effort to highlight the plight of men who are neglected by international organizations as well as government bodies within India.

The exact numbers of such cases of suicide are difficult to assess as the majority of cases go unreported. It is even tougher to figure out with exactitude how many men are suffering because of "*legal terrorism*".

Key Findings: The majority of men feel shy to come forward to report abuse, harassment, misuse of law and so most men suffer in silence and die young. There are no support groups to help men. None of the study reports of suicide by men or details highlighting atrocities on men are acknowledged by any institute, government body, and the mainstream media is reluctant to publish abuse on men or health issues concerning men in particular.

Methodology: Information for this report is sourced from the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) various secondary sources, medical journals, and various news publications, testimonies, survey statistics, etc.

Introduction: Study on Men's Health and Suicide by Men address the following questions: Why men commit suicide? How men are harassed? How legal terrorism is impacting their health? How do they suffer in silence? Why do they suffer in silence? How stressful life they lead, when they face abuse and humiliation at the hands of their beloved ones. Most of the literature collected by NGO MyNation demonstrates that there is a dearth of research on men's mental health or overall health when someone is reported to be depressed due to marital distress or a stressful relationship. There is no government body or agency for men in distress to consult

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with, no funding earmarked to encourage any organization (governmental or non-governmental) to work for men's health issues or address their socio-economic problems or to support men in distress. This study article/report is based on a review of literature obtained from legal journals, medical journals, and references from other study reports.

Worldwide around 800,000 people die due to suicide yearly, that's one person every 40 seconds. Of these 1,39,123 (18%) are residents of India. 70% of suicides are by men, and is mostly due to depression because of marital discord, which is responsible for their death. The overall male to female ratio of suicide victims for the year 2019 was 70.2: 29.8, which is more as compared to the year 2018 (68.5: 31.5). Globally, the suicide rate for men is twice than of women, that's 13.9 per 100,000 for men and 6.3 per 100,000 for women

In India, the marital status of suicide victims is observed at 66.7% (92,757 out of 1,39,123) of the suicide victims were married, which shows there is a problem with their marriage and family. As per NCRB 2019 reports, there are two major causes of suicides i.e. 'Family Problems' and 'Illness'. They also reported that Family problems and related issues were behind 32.4 percent of suicides, marriage related problems (5.5%), 70.2 were male and 29.8 females for every 100 suicide deaths. The NCRB collects national-level data from various sources. Almost 68.4 per cent of male victims were married.

Suicide Victims by Sex and Age Group during 2019

- As per data provided by States/UTs.

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Why are suicides so high amongst Indian men?

The latest health statistics paints a grim picture of India's mental health of men revealing that one person commits suicide every four minutes. The National Health 2019 raises alarm over the increasing numbers of suicide deaths to 1,39,123 in a year.

This makes it to 381 suicide deaths every day and 16 an hour.

The data also show the increasing vulnerability of Indian men versus Indian women.

Of the 1,39,123 people who killed themselves, 97,613 were men as against 41,510 women making it nearly 70.1 % of all the suicide deaths in India by men.

The number of suicides in 2000 by men has risen from 66,032 to 80,544 in 2008 and 97,613 currently. The number of male deaths from suicides is nearly double than that of females.

The survey conducted by the National Family Health Survey which throws light on unprovoked violence against men by women is evident in the face. Notwithstanding the fact that double the numbers of men commit suicide compared to women, it should not be a surprise to ask for a law to protect men as such a law for women already exist. It would be preposterous in this age of gender equality, not to have such a law. Such a law to protect men from domestic violence would act occurs to millions of those men who feel victimized and left out.

These days MEN are becoming victims of domestic violence, abuse against men in the home is on the rise. Suicide in Indian Men is rising after marriage. Suicide is on the rise because violence against men is rising, the Crime Bureau Report of India can be checked for more details.

In India Women is empowered to kill anyone and most of the time she escapes punishment because of the biased Indian laws which are favorable to Women and encourage them to take the lead in a crime. She will get away even though

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she is abetting the suicide of a man and even if she is charged, she will hardly be sentenced for 2/3 years. But if a man is convicted, he will get a life in prison which shows how the Indian Judiciary is biased.

(Ref: **CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN** - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819>)

Why more men commit suicide than women?

There are many possible reasons why middle-aged married men are more at risk of depression and depressive disorder than other groups in the population. Relationship breakdown can be more devastating for men than women. Women generally tend to be more 'emotionally literate' and can discuss their feelings with others rather than resorting to internalizing their emotions, but most of the time Men are reluctant to say that they are victims of domestic abuse.

As per a study, more than 10,000 patients a year suffer from depressive disorders, and most of them are men. Depression because of stress is far more common than most people think. Almost 20% of adults can be affected by clinically significant depression. Due to ignorance and misunderstanding many of them do not get the help they need, which is often the signs and symptoms. Depressive disorder may not always present with a low mood. Reduced concentration, losing appetite, disturbed sleeping, irritability, diminished libido, an inability to enjoy life, and extreme lethargy can often be the main symptoms and as these can develop incrementally, but most men are not ready to admit that they are depressed and avoid treatment due to their role in the society. Sometimes they even take refuge of alcohol to overcome grief, problems and when they fail they have no option other than suicide.

Not every attempt at suicide results in completion, taking one's life requires a strong will or the issues are so grave that there is no escape which leads to repeated attempts even after previous failure. Although unsuccessful first attempts are often followed by successful second attempts.

The most common risk factors for suicide are:

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Using drugs and/or alcohol to help cope with relationships, emotions, the pressure of work, or other issues

Social isolation or living alone when wife threatens to take away children with her

Not being able to form or sustain meaningful relationships

Divorce or relationship breakdowns

A history of physical and sexual abuse

Fear or threat of Imprisonment because of false cases like 498A IPC, PWDVA, Rape etc.

Loss of a loved one or losing child custody

Mental illness, particularly where this is related to depression and painful or debilitating illnesses or conditions

Suicide is most strongly associated with depression in older men, physical pain and illness, living alone, and feelings of hopelessness and guilt.

There is a lack of literature on the systemic study of violence against men and the correlates to such domestic violence in society. A few small-scale studies have shown the rates of violence against men to be similar to that of women with a prevalence of emotional violence of 32.8%. Physical violence rates against men are lesser when compared to rates against women with prevalence to be around 25.2% and sexual violence rates being less than 1%. Apart from the violence arising out of matrimonial issues, men have been reported to experience physical or psychological abuse from the natal family members of the spouse. Experiences of violence increases the risk of substance addiction, depression, and suicidal risk in men and impair their quality of life and hence the productivity at work leading to economic loss at the national-level

However, there are no laws in India to protect men from any form of domestic violence. Further men are at risk of false allegations and serious legal consequences

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by misuse of some of the laws present to protect women such as the Dowry Prohibition Act.

Most of the criminal codes (IPC/Cr.P.C) in India are blatantly biased and in favor of women. The real motive behind the enacted of special acts, rules favoring women is to appease the feminist lobby acting in the country. These acts are not targeted for the welfare of the women, rather intimidate men. Quite often such acts are poorly drafted and deliberately kept wide open to misinterpretation, being biased and favoring women in general, thus are tailor-made to abuse and misuse by disgruntled and vindictive women.

These half-baked drafts are publicly supported and intensely lobbied by the feminist mafia and so become the law of the land in double quick time without delving deep into the possible consequences. Most of such acts and amendments are introduced very quickly without taking proper measures for society to adapt to the same. They lack any clarity and appear to be created with the single motive of multiplying litigation in the country and there being little doubt that most regrettably, such a result would always be welcomed by the legal fraternity, police, and supporting departments.

There are strong social prohibitions inhibiting men from being aggressive against women and harsh legal sanctions facing men who dare to transgress but rarely any social prohibitions or legal sanctions inhibiting women from being aggressive against men - that is the reason why it is often said that it's a crime being a Male or to be born as a Male Child in India.

The government of India has enacted various one-sided and biased laws against men and favoring only Women. Unlike above-mentioned Schemes for Women, there is not a single scheme to support Men nor any law to protect Men in India.

Men who get trapped in the justice system have experienced severe social, economic, cultural, and political disadvantages. Accordingly, these determinants of well-being are considered to provide a greater understanding of the factors which have permeated and shaped their lived experiences.

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Men's experiences from their initial engagement with the police, then their experiences with lawyers, through to orders passed by Courts, clearly reveal that there exist strong perceptions of unconscious bias, unjust practices and an unholy nexus between feminists mafia, Police and Lawyers which the Government has not made any effort to address so far.

Some of the most compelling scientific evidence prove that women are no less violent than men. For more details please refer **CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN** – (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819>). But it has been seen that women's groups have threatened and bullied researchers or media or law enforcement agencies even Judges by any means possible to stop them from presenting evidence of the tendencies of women to engage, as much as men, in the perpetration of domestic violence, and additionally to file false reports of sexual harassment, rape or abuse.

The government of India is over-enthusiastic to buy into the worldwide feminist ideology. But feminism disguised as women empowerment is causing severe damage to the unifying fabric of cultural, family, and spiritual values that defines this nation. The core mindset of the Government is misandrist which is visible in the lack of support and help offered to Men in distress. Men are left out in the cold with no Law to take recourse to when victimized and are therefore more commonly resorting to suicides. The rate of Men's suicide in India is alarming with male deaths from suicides being nearly double that of females thanks to rising numbers of fake cases, ill-treatment by society, and total neglect by the Government.

(Ref: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4603151>)

As reported by NCRB most of the suicide by Men is the result of marital discord. Here are some news links we have collected. Most of the news is not published by mainstream media which are controlled by feminists or anti-men.

Social Worker Dies By Suicide Alleging Demand Of Rs 20 Lakh Alimony By Wife In Facebook Suicide Post - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/chandan-singh-verma-suicide/>

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Man Ends Life Along With Two Children After Wife Left Home Due To Financial Constraints During Lockdown - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/family-suicide-bhavnagar-gujarat/>

45-Year-Old Man Dies By Suicide Due To Illicit Affair Of Wife With Her Nephew - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-cases-india-4/>

59-Year-Old PWD Worker Dies By Suicide Alleging Constant Blackmail By Woman - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/59-year-old-pwd-worker-dies-by-suicide-delhi/>

Dalit Boy Dies By Suicide As OBC Wife Filed Rape Charges Against Him, Brother, Brother-in-Law After Returning To Her Family - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/dalit-boy-dies-by-suicide-as-obc-wife-filed-rape-charges/>

NRI Man From Gujarat Ends Life After Constant Harassment By Wife To Buy Property In USA - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/gujarat-nri-dies-by-suicide-due-to-harassment-by-wife/>

Delhi Man Ends Life Alleging Blackmail & Threats Of False Rape Case By Former Business Partner & Haryanvi Singer - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/delhi-businessman-aman-baisla-suicide/>

Ahmedabad Man Ends Life Due To Wife's Affair | Leaves Pen Drive As Evidence With Family - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-adultery/>

Head Constable Shoots Himself Due To Alleged Ongoing Problems Within Family - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-india-3/>

Prayagraj Man Shoots Himself Dead After Dispute With Wife, In-Laws - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/uttar-pradesh-man-shoots-himself-dead/>

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Man Held Captive By Wife's Family For Six Days; Returns Home & Ends Life - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/suicide/husband-suicide-7/>

Uttar Pradesh Man Ends Life After Wife Leaves Home With Children - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-6/>

28-Year-Old Man Dies Of Suicide; Leaves Video Blaming Wife, In-Laws Of Harassment - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/moradabad-man-suicide-video/>

37-Year-Old Man From Ghatkopar Ends Life; Was Allegedly Upset Over Fights At Home - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/37-year-old-man-suicide-ghatkopar-mumbai/>

Telugu TV Actor Dies Of Suicide | Partner Booked For Abetment To Suicide On Allegations By Girl's Family - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/sravani-kondapalli-suicide/>

UPSC Aspirant Ends Life After Girlfriend Of Nine Years Backed Out From Marriage - <https://www.mensdayout.com/his-story/justiceforjeet/>

Man Ends Life After Constant Threats From Wife, Family To Transfer Properties On Woman's Name - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/munish-sethi-ludhiana-suicide/>

Aditya Dash Death Case: "Psycho Lady Behind My Son's Death", Alleges Father - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/crime-has-no-gender/aditya-dash-death-case/>

Man Ends Life After Constant Harassment By Daughter-in-Law, Her Sister, Brother; Leaves Whatsapp Note - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/father-in-law-suicide-ahmedabad/>

Father-in-Law Ends Life With 6-Page Note Alleging Constant Threats Of False Cases By Daughter-in-Law & Her Family - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/father-in-law-suicide-patiala-punjab/>

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“My Parents & Wife Have Constant Tussle; Their Tussle Made My Life Difficult” – IAS Officer Ends Life - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/ias-mukesh-pandey-suicide/>

B. Tech in Electronics (IIT-Kharagpur) & IPS Kanpur Husband Ends Life Within 15-Months Of Marriage - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/surendra-kumar-das-kanpur-ips-suicide/>

“50% Of CISF Jawans Die Because Of Suicide Due To Family Related Issues”: CISF DG (2018) - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/50-cisf-jawans-suicide-due-to-family-problems/>

UP Police Officer Dies Of Suicide After Alleged Fight With Girlfriend - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/kanpur-police-officer-vikas-soni-suicide/>

BSF Soldier Dies Of Suicide In Bihar Due To Dispute With Would-Be In-Laws - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/bsf-soldier-dies-of-suicide-in-bihar-due-to-dispute-with-would-be-in-laws/>

35-Year-Old IIT Kanpur Professor Dies Of Suicide; Family Dispute Suspected - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/iit-kanpur-pramod-subramanyan-suicide/>

Bengaluru Techie Ends Life As Wife Forced Him To Transfer His Property On Her Father’s Name - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/alimony-deaths-india-mentoo/>

35-Year-Old Man & His Senior Citizen Mother End Life, After Repeated Humiliation By In-Laws - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-india-2/>

35-Year-Old Odisha Finance Service (OFS) Officer Ends Life Due To ‘Frustration Over Marital Discord’ - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/odisha-finance-service-officer-ends-life-due-to-marital-discord/>

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Man Ends Life After Wife & Mother-in-Law Constantly Harassed Him For Money - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-india/>

Saint Ends Life Accusing Couple & Women's Commission For Blackmailing Him In False Rape Case - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/alleged-false-rape/false-rape-cases-india-10/>

Retired Army Man Dies Of Suicide After Dispute With Wife During Lockdown - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicides-india/>

Uttar Pradesh Advocate Ends His Life; Names Wife & Mother-in-Law In Suicide Note - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/domestic-violence-against-men-in-india-suicide/>

Infosys Suicide Case: Family Alleges Mental Pressure & Extreme Humiliation By Live-in Girlfriend - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/infosys-suicide-case-family-alleges-mental-pressure-extreme-humiliation-by-live-in-girlfriend/>

Cricketer Mohd Shami Wanted To Commit Suicide Thrice Due To Harassment & False Cases By Wife - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/cricketer-mohd-shami-wanted-to-commit-suicide-due-to-harassment-false-cases-by-wife/>

28-Year-Old IT Professional Commits Suicide After Alleged Strained Relationship With Live-in Girlfriend - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/pune-it-professional-commits-suicide-after-strained-relationship-with-live-in-girlfriend/>

Man Who Was Working Hard To Support His Poor Family, Commits Suicide Due To False Case By Girl's Father - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/man-commits-suicide-due-to-harassment-by-police-in-false-case/>

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33-Yr-Old Hyderabad Doctor Commits Suicide As Wife Allegedly Left Him After Marriage & Did Not Return - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/hyderabad-doctor-commits-suicide-due-to-alleged-dispute-with-wife/>

Hyderabad Hospital Doctor & MD Shoots Himself After Alleged Dispute With Wife - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/hyderabad-hospital-md-shoots-himself-after-alleged-dispute-with-wife/>

Troubled With Domestic Problems, Man Jumps Into Netravati River Along With 6-Year-Old Son - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/man-jumps-into-netravati-river-along-with-6-year-old-son-mangaluru/>

RPF Jawan Shoots Himself On Moving Train; Was Troubled With Family Problems - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/rpf-jawan-shoots-himself-on-moving-train-tirupati/>

UP Minister's Security Cop Found Dead; Was Undergoing Divorce - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/up-ministers-security-cop-commits-suicide-was-undergoing-divorce/>

Army Man Ends Life Accusing Wife Of Adultery & Mother-in-Law For Spoiling His Life - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/army-man-commits-suicide-due-marital-discord-faridabad/>

Kushal Punjabi's Parents Allege Wife Demanded Huge Sum Of Alimony For Divorce - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/kushal-punjabi-suicide-alimony/>

Kota Professor Commits Suicide In Fateh Sagar Lake Due To Humiliation From Wife, Her Mother - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/kota-professor-commits-suicide-due-to-harassment-by-wife-mother-in-law/>

Fed Up Of Wife's Harassment, Husband Attempts Suicide In Mahila Police Station - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-attempts-suicide-in-mahila-police-station-bihar/>

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Software Engineer Commits Suicide Minutes Before Marriage Ceremony -

<https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/hyderabad-man-hangs-himself-before-marriage/>

Man Commits Suicide After Torture & Constant Threats Of Cases By

Girlfriend | No Arrests For Woman Yet - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/man-commits-suicide-in-jhansi-after-threats-of-cases-from-girlfriend/>

Girl Complaints To Police Alleging Boyfriend Took Money On Promise Of Marriage | Boy Commits Suicide Fearing Arrest -

<https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/suicide-police-hyderabad-tik-tok/>

MNC Manager Married In January 2019 Commits Suicide; Police Confirms

Marital Discord - <https://www.mensdayout.com/in-the-news/husband-suicide-4/>

If women die or commit suicide, by default police will take suo-moto and arrest husband and his family, but if a man commits suicide, even if he left a suicide note blaming wife and her family, police will not take any action

There is so much support for **#MeToo** Why not one for **#MenToo**?

Why do all law support / free legal-aid services only to women, why not similar laws for Men?

In India men are neither allowed to talk about their problems nor can they officially report it. For stressed men there is only one option that's ending his 'dear life'. Indian government and gender biased organizations like Ministry of Women and Child Development (WCD) / National Commission for Women (NCW) by encouraging legal terrorism are further contributing to each and every suicide which Indian men are committing.

United Nations has **UN_WOMEN** body to deal with women related issues but no **UN_MEN**, this shows the bias at top too.

Majority countries around world have special schemes and Funds to empower Women but none for men. No Ministry, no Laws, nor even helpline to counsel

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men at the critical time. World governments have enough money and funds, In India government allocated 50,000 Crore rupees in its 2019-20 budget only for women and none for men. Because for Government and ministers, only **WOMEN LIVES MATTERS**.

WHY SUCH A BIAS?

Why Not **MENS'S LIVES** too.

Reference:

Domestic Violence: The Male Struggle to Survive and Mental Health -
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4431600>

STUDY ON MEN'S HEALTH - EFFECTS OF LEGAL TERRORISM ON
MEN'S HEALTH - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4603151>

Violence Against Men – False Accusation of Sexual Harassment -
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4445147>

CRIMES BY INDIAN WOMEN - <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4537819>

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